

Fabrication and characterization of Lipidic Nanocarriers for Rivastigmine : A Review

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Abstract:

Rivastigmine, a reversible carbamate acetylcholinesterase inhibitor, is a first-line drug for Alzheimer disease. However, its conventional oral dosage form exhibits poor bioavailability, extensive first-pass metabolism, short half life, inadequate blood-brain barrier permeability, and cholinergic side effect necessitating frequent dosing and reducing patient compliance. To address these limitations, lipid nanocarriers have gained attention as promising drug delivery system. This review summarizes recent advances in the fabrication and characterization of lipidic nanocarriers for rivastigmine, including solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN), nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC), nanoemulsions, and liposomes. Emphasis is placed on preparation techniques such as high-pressure homogenization, solvent evaporation, microemulsion, and ultrasonication, along with key characterization parameters like particle size, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency, drug release, and ex vivo permeation. Among these systems, NLCs are most promising due to higher drug loading, improved stability, and enhanced brain targeting. This review highlights the potential of lipidic nanocarriers to improve rivastigmine delivery and therapeutic efficacy in Alzheimer therapy.

Key words: Rivastigmine, lipidic nanocarriers, Alzheimer's disease, Blood-brain barrier, Fabrication, Characterization, intranasal.

Introduction:

Alzheimer's disease is a brain disease that become worse over time. Never cells in the brain slowly die, so memory and thinking power are lost. Alzheimer's disease can occur at any age, but 95% of cases are people with above 65 years of age (Late-onset) and about 5% of cases are also affected by Alzheimer's disease with below 65 year age (Early-onset).

There are some main reason Alzheimer's disease happen after age 65:

- Protein clearance slows down with age
- Accumulated lifetime damage
- Blood - brain barrier become leaky
- Vascular changes
- Genetic and ApoE4 risk expression
- Age-related brain changes
- lifestyle factors

Alzheimer's disease is the main reason for dementia, which means loss of memory and reasoning ability. It may progress to a totally vegetative state where patient cannot do anything. In Alzheimer's disease, the brain shrinks. This is called atrophy of cortex and subcortex. A sticky protein called beta-amyloid collects outside the brain cells. This forms clumps called senile plaques or amyloid plaques. These plaques block communication between neurons and damage them.

Inside the brain cells, another protein called 'tau' becomes abnormal. It forms twisted fibers called neurofibrillary tangles. These tangles block transport of nutrients inside neurons, so cells die.

In normal brain, old proteins are cleared away. In Alzheimer's disease, the brain cannot remove beta-amyloid and tau properly, so they build up. In some people, the brain makes too much of these proteins. Both problems lead to death of neurons. When neurons die, brain function is lost permanently.

The biggest chemical changes in Alzheimer's disease is loss of acetylcholine. Acetylcholine is needed for memory and learning. This is called cholinergic deficiency. This is why drug rivastigmine are given to increase acetylcholine. Current therapeutic strategies primarily focus on symptomatic management through restoration of cholinergic function.

Clinical manifestations :

Cognitive symptoms

- Agnosia
- Anomia
- Amnesia
- Apraxia
- Aphasia

Non-cognitive symptoms

- Apathy
- Agitation
- Depression
- Delusions
- Wandering

Diagnosis:

- Cognitive test
- Blood test
- MRI scan
- PET scan
- CSF biomarkers
- Blood biomarkers

Prevention :

- Use Hearing aids
- Hypertension control
- Exercise & Healthy diet
- Smoking cessation
- Treat cataracts
- Ldl control
- Blood sugar control
- Sleep hygiene

Treatment:

- AchE inhibitors
- NMDA antagonist
- Anti-Amyloid

Contra-indications of drugs for Alzheimer's disease:

- Anticholinergics
- Benzodiazepines
- Antipsychotic drugs
- First-generation Antihistamines
- Muscle relaxants
- H2 blockers

RIVASTIGMINE

Rivastigmine is chemically a carbamate compound made from physostigmine, reversible cholinesterase inhibitor approved by FDA for the treatment of mild to moderate Alzheimer's disease. Which is highly lipid soluble, dissolves well in fats and lipids. Because the blood-brain barrier is made of lipids, lipid-soluble drugs can cross it easily. So rivastigmine can reach the brain without much difficulty compared to water-soluble drugs.

It works by inhibiting two enzymes- acetylcholinesterase AChE and butyrylcholinesterase BuChE. Both enzymes break down acetylcholine in the brain. In Alzheimer's disease, acetylcholine level is low, so we block these enzymes to increase acetylcholine concentration in the brain.

There are different forms of AChE enzyme. G1 isoform is mainly present in the brain cortex and hippocampus, which are areas affected in Alzheimer's.

Rivastigmine blocks G1 form more strongly than other forms. This gives better action in the brain with less effect on other body parts.

Rivastigmine increases acetylcholine mainly in the brain, so memory and thinking improve. But it has less effect on acetylcholine in other body parts like stomach and heart. This means fewer side effects like salivation, diarrhea, or slow heart rate compared to other drugs like physostigmine.

Rivastigmine attaches a carbamyl group to the AChE enzyme. This attachment breaks very slowly. So even after the drug is removed from blood, the enzyme remains blocked for up to 10 hours. This gives long duration of action in the brain.

This half-life of rivastigmine in blood plasma is only 2 hours. Half-life means time taken for drug concentration to become half. So drug disappears from blood quickly. But because it binds to brain enzyme for 10 hours, the effect on brain lasts much longer than blood levels. This is called hit and run action.

However, the therapeutic efficacy of rivastigmine is limited by several biopharmaceutical challenges when given as conventional oral tablet or capsules.

The major limitations of rivastigmine include poor oral bioavailability of approximately 36% due to extensive first-pass metabolism, short elimination half-life of 1.5 hours requiring frequent dosing, and poor penetration across the blood-brain barrier. Frequent oral administration leads to fluctuations in plasma concentration, causing severe dose-dependent gastrointestinal side effects such as nausea, vomiting, anorexia, and weight loss. These side effects result in poor patient compliance, especially in elderly patients who are the main population affected by Alzheimer's disease.

To overcome these limitations, novel drug delivery systems are being explored to improve brain targeting and reduce systemic side effects.

LIPIDIC NANOCARRIERS

Lipidic nanocarriers are biocompatible, biodegradable drug delivery systems composed of physiological lipids that mimic endogenous components, Nanocarriers are nanoscale drug delivery systems, typically 1-1000nm in size, designed to improve the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profiles of therapeutic agents. These systems includes liposomes, solid lipid nanocarriers (SLNs), nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), and nanoemulsion. By encapsulating drugs, nanocarriers protect them from enzymatic degradation, enhance solubility and stability.

These systems offer distinct advantages for central nervous system deliver: high drug loading for lipophilic compounds, protection of encapsulated drug from enzymatic degradation, and the ability to cross the blood-brain barrier via lipid-mediated endocytosis. They can also reduce dosing frequency by providing prolonged drug release and minimize peripheral side effects by targeted delivery.

Therefore, the present research work is aimed at fabrication and characterization of rivastigmine-loaded lipidic nanocarriers to enhance brain bioavailability, sustain drug release, reduce dose and dosing frequency, and improve patient compliance in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

Advantages

- Enhanced blood-brain barrier
- High biocompatibility
- Low toxicity
- Improved drug loading & stability
- Controlled & sustained drug release
- Versatility in administration routes
- Reduced peripheral side effects
- Regulatory acceptance

Disadvantage

- Limited drug loading for hydrophilic compounds
- Gelation & particle growth

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